

Received / Makale Geliş Tarihi 22.09.2025
Published / Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.12.2025
Volume (Issue) Cilt (Sayı) 9 (61)
pp / ss 1512-1519

Research Article / Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.18117976
Mail: editor@pejoss.com

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Comparative Analysis of Interior Design Preferences in Two Different Cafe Spaces İç Mekân Tasarım Tercihlerinin İki Farklı Kafe Mekânında Karşılaştırmalı Olarak İrdelenmesi

ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine the comparative effects of design choices made in commercial interior arrangements on user perception and spatial experience through a case study. The study's material consists of the Belize Cafe (Nostalgic Theme) and the Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe (Innovative Theme), both located in Bilecik's city center and featuring distinct design identities. The study first analyzed design elements (color, light, furniture, material) within a theoretical framework. Subsequently, data were collected through on-site observations and a quantitative survey method administered to cafe customers. The study is an analysis that combines quantitative and qualitative approaches to investigate the relationship between interior design components and user perception.

Keywords: Interior Design, Cafe Design, User Experience, Spatial Perception, Design Preferences.

ÖZET

Bu araştırma, ticari iç mekan düzenlemelerinde yapılan tasarım tercihlerinin kullanıcı algısı ve mekansal deneyim üzerindeki etkilerini karşılaştırmalı bir durum çalışması ile incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Çalışmanın materyalini, Bilecik il merkezinde yer alan, farklı tasarım kimliklerine sahip Belize Kafe (Nostaljik Tema) ve Tarz-1 Hayal Kafe (Yenilikçi Tema) örnekleri oluşturmaktadır. Çalışmada, tasarım öğeleri (renk, ışık, mobilya, malzeme) kuramsal bir çerçevede incelenmiş; ardından saha gözlemleri ve kafe müşterileri üzerinde yürütülen nicel anket yöntemiyle veri toplanmıştır. Çalışma, iç mekan tasarım unsurları ile kullanıcı algısı arasındaki ilişkiyi incelemek üzere nicel ve nitel yaklaşımları birleştiren bir analiz çalışmasıdır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İç Mekan Tasarımı, Kafe Tasarımı, Kullanıcı Deneyimi, Mekansal Algı, Tasarım Tercihleri.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interior design is an interdisciplinary field focused on shaping physical spaces—where daily life occurs—to meet aesthetic, functional, and psychological needs, placing human-space interaction at its center (Zeisel, 2006). This field spans from residences and workplaces to commercial and social venues (cafes, restaurants, etc.), each presenting unique design requirements specific to its purpose. Design choices made within a space fundamentally affect not only its visual appeal but also the user experience, spatial perception, and functionality (Ching, 2015).

The interior design process is a comprehensive problem-solving activity that aims to meet users' ergonomic and emotional expectations, going beyond mere aesthetic concerns. In this context, design elements gain varying weights based on the space's core function. For instance, in a cafe setting, biophilic elements, warm color palettes, and natural textures might be prioritized to evoke feelings of socialization and relaxation among customers. Conversely, in concentration- and efficiency-focused environments like offices, neutral colors, highly functional furniture systems, and practical lighting solutions are preferred.

This illustrates the critical importance of design choices in achieving space-function harmony (Aksoy, 2017).

This study aims to examine design preferences in interior arrangements from a multidimensional perspective. These preferences will be analyzed concerning their impact on the overall atmosphere, user satisfaction, and psychological perception of the space. The central components of this study are color psychology and usage, material selection, furniture ergonomics and layout, lighting strategies, and decorative elements. The interaction of these elements with social, cultural, and socioeconomic factors, and the resulting spatial identity they create, will be detailed.

In this context, the study will conduct a case study using the Belize Cafe and Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe examples, which represent differing design approaches. These two contrasting cafe themes aim to demonstrate concretely how design preferences create different user experiences even in spaces with the same function, supporting theoretical knowledge through practical applications.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section focuses on the concept of space, design elements, and their psychological interactions, which form the foundation of design preferences in interior arrangements. It provides a theoretical basis explaining how design approaches, specifically in cafes, shape user experience and spatial identity.

2.1. Spatial Experience and the Concept of Interior Space

Interior spaces are areas with physical, functional, and emotional contexts where people live, work, socialize, and rest. The concept of space is not limited to three-dimensional physical arrangement; it also shapes users' perceptions and experiences (Bitner, 1992). Especially in commercial venues with intense social interaction, such as cafes, interior design goes beyond mere functionality, determining the space's atmosphere by creating an emotional and psychological impact on users.

The main goal in cafe design is to meet users' needs both physical (ergonomics/comfort) and psychological (atmosphere/belonging) and to offer an attractive and relaxing environment that encourages social interaction (Özdemir, 2018). In this regard, interior design choices must align with the space's cultural and social environment, establishing a connection with the local identity to foster users' sense of belonging (Özdemir, 2018).

2.2. Core Components of Interior Design

The fundamental components that directly affect the overall aesthetics, functionality, and user experience of an interior space can be grouped as color, lighting, furniture, material, and layout (arrangement). These elements must work in harmony to create an atmosphere suitable for the space's intended use (Ching, 2015).

2.3. Functionality, Aesthetics, and Ergonomics

The main aspects to consider in interior design can be summarized as functionality (the space serving its purpose), aesthetic values (visual appeal), and ergonomics/comfort (user convenience) (Azzuhri & Tanjung, 2017).

Functionality: The placement of furniture and decorative elements must allow users to move freely and enable all areas of the space to be used with optimum efficiency (Özdemir, 2018).

Aesthetics: The selection of color, texture, and materials determines the space's mood. The design's aesthetic dimension leaves a strong impression on the user (Ching, 2015).

Ergonomics and Comfort: Especially in cafes, factors like seating arrangement, table height, and lighting should aim for a high level of comfort to ensure users spend long, enjoyable periods in the space (Bitner, 1992).

2.4. Psychological Effects of Color and Light Selection

Color and light are the most critical factors affecting the atmosphere of social venues like cafes and users' emotional states (Birren, 2006).

Table 1. Detailing Factors Affecting Psychology in Interior Spaces

Element	Type	Effect
Light	Natural Light	Promotes positive mood, increased energy, and social interaction (Boubekri, 2014).
	Warm Light	Creates a comfortable, intimate, and inviting atmosphere (Haghshenas, 2017).
	Cool Light	Imparts a sense of modernity and dynamism; typically used in areas requiring focus (Haghshenas, 2017).
Color	Warm Colors (Red, Orange)	Creates an energetic atmosphere, supports social interaction, and can increase the feeling of hunger in commercial spaces (Birren, 2006).
	Cool Colors (Blue, Green)	Provides a calming and relaxing effect. Evokes natural elements, offering tranquility (Bennett, 2013).
	Neutral Colors (Beige, Grey)	Elicits a sense of cleanliness, order, and spaciousness. Fundamental to minimalist designs (Bennett, 2013).

A harmonious combination of these two elements can create vibrancy at the entrance of a space and a soft, relaxing ambiance in the seating areas (Birren, 2006).

2.5. Lighting Design: Types and Functions

Lighting design in cafe structures does not merely fulfill the function of sight; it also creates visual hierarchy and determines the emotional tone of the space.

Lighting is fundamentally used in four functions:

1. **General (Ambient) Lighting:** Provides the general level of illumination in the space (ceiling lamps, spotlights).
2. **Task Lighting:** Illumination that enables focus on a specific task (reading lamps on a table).
3. **Accent Lighting:** Highlights focal points such as artworks, decorative objects, or architectural details.
4. **Decorative Lighting:** Aesthetic fixtures used to create visual appeal.

Proper lighting placement, especially with dimming systems, provides spatial flexibility across different times of day and needs, thereby increasing user satisfaction (Kroelinger, 2013; Pawling, 2020).

2.6. Furniture, Material, and Accessory Preferences

Furniture, materials, and accessories, being the embodied representation of interior design, are core elements that define the space's identity and the comfort it offers. Furniture is vital for the cafe's functionality, aesthetics, and identity. Functionality, comfort, durability, and the overall aesthetic understanding (style) of the space are the primary determining factors in furniture selection (Nelson, 2017; Millet, 2016).

Different design approaches directly influence furniture selection (Stern, 2018):

Modern Design: Clean lines, minimalism. Simple and neutral-colored furniture combined with metal and wood.

Industrial Design: Raw and unfinished appearance. Heavy and durable furniture made of metal, concrete, and dark wood materials.

Rustic Design: Naturalness, warmth. Natural wood tones, large and intimate seating areas in cream and earth colors.

Minimalist Design: Simple and functional. Light-colored wood or metal furniture with simple lines and minimal detail.

2.7. Material, Texture, and Accessory Usage

Material and Texture: Selected materials (wood, stone, glass, metal, etc.) affect the space's durability and thermal/acoustic comfort. Natural materials create a warm and intimate effect, while synthetic or modern materials impart a more dynamic feel. Contrasts in texture and material add depth and richness to the space (Ching, 2015; Bıyıklıoğlu, 2013).

Accessories (plants, artwork, decorative lighting) complement the space's aesthetic, create spatial identity, and offer users a sense of comfort and personalization (Naylor, 2020). The use of plants (biophilic design), in particular, improves indoor air quality and enhances the feeling of connection with nature (Stern, 2015).

2.8. Layout and Social Interaction

Layout is the strategic arrangement of all elements that ensures the space is functionally and aesthetically efficient. Layout also determines customers' social interaction:

Social Areas: Round tables for intimate conversations; long tables for group activities (Gifford, 2007).

Flow: The furniture arrangement should ensure efficient movement areas for both customers and staff, eliminating unnecessary difficulties, as well as providing continuous and ergonomic circulation areas for efficient service provision by staff (Lawson, 2006).

Diversity: Diversity should be offered to meet different needs, such as individual seating, group areas, a bar, and relaxation corners.

3. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research was conducted using two cafe venues with different themes, Belize Cafe and Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe, located in the city center of Bilecik, situated on the southeastern border of the Marmara Region. Both selected cafes are important focal points of urban social life due to their locations in the Bilecik city center and their easy accessibility.

Belize Cafe: Located on the main street in İstiklal Mahallesi, on the upper floor of a commercial building. Its location on the main street ensures direct contact with heavy traffic flow and commercial activity.

Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe: Situated on the top floor of a residential building, dominating the city center. This location, surrounded by side roads rather than main roads, potentially offers a more isolated atmosphere with a city view.

Figure 1. Location of Belize and Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe

The primary purpose of selecting these two spaces is to compare the differences in user perception created by distinct design languages and spatial environments in commercial areas with similar functions.

Research Model: The basic research model relies on a comparative examination of the interior design preferences of the two selected cafe examples. The methodology applied consists of two stages:

Observation and Space Analysis: In the first stage of the study, the researcher conducted a detailed space analysis by visiting both cafes on-site. This analysis covered the processes of photographing, measuring, and categorizing design elements based on the core design components identified in the introduction (color, lighting, furniture, material, and layout). This stage ensured the objective documentation of design preferences.

Quantitative Data Collection (Survey Method): In the second stage, a survey was conducted to determine customers' subjective perceptions, satisfaction levels, and psychological responses to the interior design. The survey's target audience consisted of individuals residing in Bilecik and visiting cafes, including university students, academic staff, and residents.

Due to the difficulty in determining the size of the user population, it was not possible to set a precise number for the total universe. Therefore, the survey was administered to a large number of people, and 31 responses were evaluated.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

This section presents the findings from on-site observations and quantitative data collection (survey) regarding the interior arrangements of Belize Cafe and Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe in Bilecik.

In line with the survey results, 45.2% of participants stated that they pay attention to the overall concept of a cafe design, 19.4% prioritized color choices, and 12.9% stated that decorative accessories and lighting were important. Furthermore, in response to another question, 38.7% of participants stated that the most important feature of a cafe atmosphere for them was a relaxed, natural atmosphere, 32.3% preferred a warm, intimate atmosphere, 19.4% preferred an artistic, inspiring atmosphere, and 9.7% preferred a modern, chic design. Additionally, 61.3% stated that natural light was important, and 32.3% preferred dim lighting. In a question regarding the importance of wall decorations in cafe spaces, 48.4% of participants stated it was important. Moreover, 54.8% of participants answered that the selection and placement of furniture in the space were essential.

A large majority of participants (74.2%) found the Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe design more appealing, while 25.8% preferred the Belize Cafe design. These results indicate a strong inclination toward young, innovative designs.

Critical Role of Design: Participants emphasized that the interior design of a cafe significantly affects their interest in the space and their decision to revisit (loyalty).

Determining Factors: The three fundamental elements determining users' spatial experience were highlighted as aesthetic design, functionality, and ergonomic comfort.

4.1. Belize Cafe Design Characteristics

Belize Cafe has adopted a predominantly retro, nostalgic theme, offering a warm, intimate atmosphere.

Figure 2. Images from the Interior Design of Belize Cafe (Original 2025)

Figure 3. Images from Belize Cafe (Original 2025)

Table 2. Belize Cafe Design Characteristics

Design Element	Distinctive Features	User Perception
Theme and Atmosphere	Retro / Nostalgic Identity	Preferred by participants who value sensitivity to the past and traditional values.
Color and Material	Wooden furniture, soft (pastel) color tones.	Provided a natural and inviting feeling, which forms the main character of the space.
Lighting	Dim, soft lighting with a warm color temperature.	Supported a relaxing and tranquil environment.
Decorative Elements	Wall writings, wall photographs, and artistic touches.	Added a personal touch and story to the space.

4.2. Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe Design Characteristics

Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe has been praised for its innovative, modern, and experimental design, resulting in an inspiring space enriched with artistic details.

Figure 4. Images from the Interior Design of Tarz-I Hayal (Original 2025)

Figure 5. Images from Tarz-I Hayal Cafe (Original 2025)

Table 3. Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe Design Characteristics

Design Element	Distinctive Features	User Perception
Theme and Atmosphere	Creative and Artistic Approach	Created a dynamic and inspiring spatial identity. Appealed especially to the younger demographic.
Lighting and Arrangement	Dim, yet focused on specific corners with creative fixtures.	Created a sense of personalized areas in the space, supporting privacy and focus.
Color and Decoration	Vibrant color palette, handmade decorative objects, and wall writings.	Created an energetic and distinct atmosphere, highlighting the experimental design.

Comparative Analysis: The comparative analysis of the two cafe examples clarified the impact of design identity on user expectations:

Identity Comparison: Belize Cafe reflects a traditional and reassuring identity, whereas Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe offers a more experimental, inspiring, and creativity-fostering identity.

User Preferences: Belize Cafe was found appealing by individuals seeking nostalgia and calmness, while Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe appeals to the younger demographic open to visual stimuli, preferring innovation and distinctiveness.

Areas for Improvement:

Belize Cafe: It was suggested that the existing design, based on nostalgia, be supported with modern touches (e.g., contemporary artworks or minimalist lighting fixtures) to adapt to current trends. This would increase the potential to appeal to a broader audience.

Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe: Despite its high aesthetic value, participants indicated that it requires some adjustments in terms of functionality and comfort (especially furniture ergonomics and the fluidity of the layout).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research aimed to deeply analyze the effects of interior design preferences on user perception and spatial experience, utilizing the Belize Cafe (Nostalgic Theme) and Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe (Innovative Theme) examples in Bilecik. The findings demonstrate that spatial identity is constructed through design elements, which play a determining role in user satisfaction. The research confirmed that the core design components identified in the theoretical framework (light, color, furniture, layout) play a critical role in the success of commercial venues.

The quantitative findings revealed that the distinctly separated design identities of the two spaces successfully appeal to different demographic groups (Belize Cafe: those seeking nostalgia; Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe: the younger demographic seeking creativity and innovation).

The most critical factor ensuring user satisfaction was determined to be the simultaneous presentation of the three elements: aesthetic appeal, functional arrangement, and ergonomic comfort. Despite Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe's high aesthetic perception, its user experience potential fell short due to deficiencies in comfort and layout. The intense emotional atmosphere created by both spaces (Belize's warm atmosphere, Tarz-1 Hayal's energetic structure) directly influenced visitors' tendency to return.

According to the research findings, the design identity of a space plays a significant role in users' decisions to revisit and their overall satisfaction. A large majority of participants (74.2%) preferred the dynamic and creative atmosphere of Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe, while Belize Cafe was found successful in appealing to individuals seeking nostalgia and intimacy. The analyses showed that the basic elements determining user experience are the triad of aesthetic appeal, functionality, and ergonomic comfort.

In conclusion, both spaces were found to increase user satisfaction by creating intense emotional atmospheres. However, Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe was found to need improvement in functionality and furniture comfort, while Belize Cafe needs its theme enriched with modern touches.

In light of the results obtained, concrete recommendations that may shed light on the design processes of similar commercial venues are as follows:

5.1. Recommendations for Belize Cafe (Appealing to a Wider Audience)

Theme Integration: The nostalgic theme should be preserved but blended with modern and contemporary design elements (e.g., contemporary artworks, minimalist lighting fixtures) to create a rich visual contrast. This will increase the potential to appeal to a broader audience.

Lighting Strategy: Variable light intensities specific to different functional areas of the space (Task Lighting) should be used to add depth and flexibility to the space.

5.2. Recommendations for Tarz-1 Hayal Cafe (Functional Optimization)

Ergonomics and Layout: Without compromising the creative atmosphere, furniture selection and layout arrangement should be optimized for functionality and comfort. Modular seating areas that allow users to spend time comfortably and support various forms of social interaction (individual work, group conversations) should be designed.

Lighting Diversity: The creative effect of dim lighting should be maintained, but brighter, focus-assisting lighting solutions (task lighting) should be added, especially for customers who come to read or work in the evenings.

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